

PROVIDING EMPLOYMENT OF THE POPULATION IN RURAL AREAS IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Abstract: In this article, the author's opinion on some problems of ensuring employment of the population in rural conditions and their solutions is presented. In addition, suggestions and recommendations on digitalization of this field are presented.

Key words: Digital service, digital economy, digitization, employment, workforce, active population, reforms, programs.

ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЕ ЗАНЯТОСТИ СЕЛЬСКОГО НАСЕЛЕНИЯ В ЦИФРОВОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ

Аннотация: В данной статье представлен авторский взгляд на некоторые проблемы обеспечения занятости населения в сельских условиях и пути их решения. Кроме того, представлены предложения и рекомендации по цифровизации данной сферы.

Ключевые слова: цифровая услуга, цифровая экономика, цифровизация, занятость, рабочая сила, активное население, реформы, программы.

INTRODUCTION

Today, in the conditions of digitization of the economy in our country, the work to ensure local employment is becoming an urgent issue on the agenda. Because the problem of ensuring the employment of the population is one of the most important indicators of the socio-economic development of the society. Also, in order to increase the employment of the population in the framework of the reforms carried out in recent years, to increase the real monetary income and purchasing power of the population, to further reduce the number of low-income families and the level of differences in income, to create new jobs, to ensure the balance of the labor market and the development of infrastructure, and to reduce the level of unemployment. defined as a task.

At the same time, it can be seen in the example of developed countries that providing employment to the population in rural areas is the main pillar for the growth of the country's economy. According to preliminary data, the permanent population of our republic is 36017770 as of December 2022. And 13538876 of them are listed as employed population in the Economy¹. It is clear from this that providing permanent employment to the population in our country and attracting them to work is one of the priority directions of the main state policy.

Analysis of literature on the topic:

The issue of the relative development of population employment was raised by G. Becker, T. Shults, A. Sen, O. I. Kosenko, D. N. Karpukhin. At the same time, methodological foundations of the labor market and employment of the population A. Smith, D. Ricardo, J.B. Sey, demand and supply of labor force, entrepreneurship characteristics - D. Keynes, D. Cohen, M. Mintz, P. Samuelson, A. Marshall, M. Friedman and others have contributed to the scientific work of the scientist. A. Smith in his work "Research on the nature and causes of the wealth of nations"

¹ State Statistics Committee

expresses the opinion that the concept of employment is determined by the activities and aspirations of people through their personal economic interests.

Russian scientist A.G. Gryaznov calls "employment a set of economic relations related to employment and participation in economic activities." Economist V.A. Pivlenkov defined that "employment of the population is citizens who have reached the legal age and are currently engaged in activities that bring income in the form of material or money."

Academician K. Kh. Abdurahmanov, one of the economists of our country, defines it as follows: "Employment is the activity of citizens that is related to meeting their personal and social needs that does not conflict with the laws, and which brings them wages and income." Economist D.A. Ortikova considers the organization and functioning of the labor market as an important link in ensuring and supporting employment in the market economy.

According to A.Olmasov and A.Vahobov, one of our scientists, "Employment is the employment of people who have the ability to work and are eager to work, and engage in useful work." In our opinion, population employment is a social relationship that provides the population with a place of work and at the same time with the necessary means for a person to live.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The results of the scientific work of our country and foreign scientists on the theory of ensuring employment of the population, as well as the decrees and decisions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on ensuring employment of the population and increasing the well-being of the population constitute the results.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

According to the first priority direction of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" No. targeted training of qualified specialists, formation of skills in management basics, employment provision, banking and finance, real estate, land, animal husbandry and poultry breeding in all neighborhood chairmen and assistant governors². For this, first of all, it is necessary to determine the components of agricultural land and divide it into fruit growing, fishing, production or other sectors.

If we look at the end of January-September 2022, the amount of gross added value created in agriculture, forestry and fisheries in Samarkand region alone is 17182.0 billion. amounted to soums and increased by 3.9% compared to January-September 2021³. The Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations and the Ministry of Finance have developed a "Roadmap" to ensure the employment of the population. The "Roadmap" was approved by the decision of the President "On measures to improve and increase the efficiency of work to ensure the employment of the population" published in UzA⁴.

Perform the following important tasks in the decision:

- establishment of greenhouses, purchase of seeds, seedlings, livestock and poultry, agricultural inventory and equipment, irrigation devices (pumps, artesian wells, etc.) in order to develop production in private estates and farms;

² Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022 - 2026", No. PD-60 dated 28.01.2022

³ State Statistics Committee

⁴ <https://www.norma.uz/>

- purchase of modern mini-equipment and raw materials for processing, storage and packaging of agricultural products, building materials, production of food and non-food consumer goods;
- establishment and equipping of enterprises operating in the service sector, especially in household, repair, educational, medical, information-communication and other high-demand sectors;
- development of home economics in rural districts, especially among women;
- production specialization of districts and cities, available mineral raw materials, land, agriculture and other resources, etc. are defined;

In the field of the adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Employment of the Population", Presidential decrees, decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers and a number of regulatory legal documents on ensuring employment of the population and effective use of the workforce is creating the ground for important changes. It should be noted that a number of problems regarding attracting the population to work, creating new jobs and effective use of labor force in rural areas are still relevant.

It is appropriate to use the data of the State Statistics Committee and the results of the study of employment issues of the Ministry of Labor in order to objectively assess the situation in the labor market, determine the number of working-age population in accordance with international standards, and formulate the procedure for developing the balance of labor resources. In addition, as stated in the paragraph of the general rules of the methodology for calculating the labor resources, employment and employment of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the calculation of the unemployed population in need of employment, "Labor resources, employment and employment of the Republic of Uzbekistan" development of the balance and unemployed population in need of employment calculation, methodology (hereinafter referred to as Methodology) to work determines the procedure for calculating the number of the unemployed population in need of employment by region, studying the employment of the population and developing the balance of labor resources, employment and employment of the population. the methodology is calculated and used to form and calculate the balance of labor resources, employment and employment of the population, as well as to estimate the number of employed population for each next calendar year⁵."

Our country is experiencing an important period related to the change of economic sectors in rural areas, digitization, mobilization of this process, and the introduction of artificial intelligence into the field. By 2022, almost a quarter of the world's GDP is predicted to be in the digital sector, and the need to develop a new economy for employment in rural areas becomes even more clear. In the current conditions of socio-economic development related to the implementation of economic reforms in rural areas in our country, the priority task is to develop and implement the goals and objectives of the population employment policy that is in line with the conditions of economic development.

Employment of the population in the villages, various forms and directions of labor activities related to ensuring the modern quality of life, creating conditions for the development of human capital, and ensuring the transition of the division of labor to a relatively high level in rural conditions. includes. It is impossible to ensure social stability, further progress through economic

⁵ <https://lex.uz/docs/-3469433>

reforms in rural areas, and ensure a modern labor market without ensuring reasonable employment of the rural population.

In addition, the President signed the decision of 28.04.2021 "On the state program on the creation of new jobs in 2021 and assistance to the employment of the population". Based on the document, the following were approved:

- State program on creating new jobs and supporting employment of the population in 2021;
- A new system for effective organization of labor activities of citizens employed in temporary, seasonal and one-time jobs.

CONCLUSIONS

To sum up, in the era of digital economy, using the experience of foreign practices on socio-economic mechanisms of increasing the employment of the rural population, which are convenient for our country, it is effective and faster to increase the level of employment of the population.

Scientific research and analysis of the experience of foreign practices on the organizational economic and social mechanisms of increasing the employment of the population in the conditions of the digital economy, using the advanced aspects of the experience of these countries, which are suitable for our country, makes it possible to identify effective and promising directions for increasing the level of employment of the population and apply them in practice.

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